

STEP LADDER (DAILY STEPS PROGRESSION)

Women-centered, bilingual, remote-ready materials for working-age adults

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PURPOSE

Increase daily movement safely and realistically by progressing step counts in small, sustainable increments—**designed with working-age women in mind** (caregiving, shifts, time constraints), suitable for all adults.

WHO

Adults 18–64 (office, front-desk/retail, hospitality, security, remote work). Any step counter/app works.

HOW TO START (BASELINE)

1. Wear a step counter for **3 typical days**.
2. Calculate your **average** = baseline.
3. Use the **ladder** to set **weekly targets**.

STEP LADDER (CHOOSE YOUR ROW BY BASELINE)

- **< 4,000** → W1: **4,500** · W2: **5,500** · W3: **6,500** · W4+: **7,000–8,000**
- **4,000–5,499** → W1: **5,500** · W2: **6,500** · W3: **7,000** · W4+: **7,500–8,500**
- **5,500–6,999** → W1: **6,500** · W2: **7,000** · W3: **7,500** · W4+: **8,000–9,000**
- **7,000–8,999** → W1: **+500** · W2: **+1,000** · W3: **Hold** · W4+: **+500 optional (8,000–10,000)**
- **≥ 9,000** → W1: **Maintain ≥ 9,000** most days · W2: **+10-min brisk walk × 3/wk** · W3: **Maintain** · W4+: **+500 optional**

Good to know: Any increase helps. If a week is tough, **hold** or **step back** one rung and continue.

MICRO-STRATEGIES (ADD 200–400 STEPS AT A TIME)

- **2–5 min** post-meal walks (breakfast/lunch/dinner)
- Park farther; take **stairs** when safe
- **Walking calls** or a 5-min “loop” before/after meetings
- Pair a short walk with a routine (coffee, restroom)
- **March in place** or indoor laps during breaks

Educational—does not replace medical care.

EFFORT (RPE 0–10)

Aim for **light-moderate (RPE 2–5)**. A brisk walk = you can talk but not sing.

QUICK TRACKING

Daily goal: _____ steps

Mon Tue Wed Thu Fri Sat Sun

Notes: _____

Stop Signs: Stop with chest pain, dizziness, unusual shortness of breath, or sharp joint pain. Pregnancy/medical conditions: adapt (low-impact) and follow clinician advice.